

This project aimed to analyze the traffic related problems in Long Bazaar in Vellore, India which is one of the most congested places in the city. The long bazaar is one of the main commercial streets in the city which is busy throughout the day especially during the weekends. During initial reconnaissance survey, the study stretch was visited during various times of the day during both weekdays and weekends and all the traffic related problems were noted. It was found that one of the major traffic related problems was side friction, which means the reduction of original road width due to various factors like on-street parking both on median and curd side, presence of various road side shops occupying the main carriageway itself, loading and unloading of goods during peak hours, etc. It was also found that the carriageway width at Long bazaar road was varying much at different locations along the entire stretch and thus necessitates the need for redesign of entire road stretch.

Keywords: Traffic problems, Carriageway width, Side friction, Remedial measures, On-street Parking.